

Articulating Manager's Skills And Employee Performance Management Through Artificial Intelligence

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 23, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: October 25, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Artificial Intelligence, Manager competencies, Information Technology, Middle Level Managers</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5646563</p>	<p><i>The study aims at examining the relationship of managerial skills (technical skills, human skills, and conceptual skills) and employee performance for re-testing the Katz theory of managerial skills. Further the moderating role of artificial intelligence is examined in the IT Company's context to examine whether the managerial skills are influenced using artificial intelligence tools?The quantitative method with cross sectional design was used to record perceptions of the middle level managers. 240 managers working in IT companies were sampled for their perceptions through questionnaires and Structural Equation Modeling was applied for analysis.Although AI is a new term, but a good number of people were aware of the concept of the "artificial intelligence". The results revealed that the use of artificial intelligence in the organizations is positively related to manage employee performance.This study provides a path for the learning and understanding of artificial intelligence in the context of developing country. This study helps in understanding that the AI tools are as important as the original skills of the managers and at the same time help managers to boost their skills.The relationship of Katz managerial skills set is examined with employees (middle level managers) performance in the presence of artificial intelligence, showing the novelty of idea examined. The Iraqi economy is suffering from many problems and crises caused by the wrong policies, unjustified wars and the economic blockade imposed by the Security Council of the United Nations(UNSC) using Article 41 of the Charter of the United Nations, by resolution 661 (661) of 6/4/1990, issued by the executive branch of the Organization of State, which called on all countries to refrain from any trade exchanges with Iraq, except for medical and food supplies, and this decision was the result of the invasion of Kuwaiti territory by Iraqi forces.</i></p>

Introduction

Managing employee performance is the main concern for individuals and organizations (Buil, I., Martínez, &Matute, 2019; Reb, Chaturvedi, Narayanan, &Kudesia, 2019) that heavily depend upon the factors prevailing in the work environment (Rizwan, Tariq, Hassan, & Sultan, 2014). Moreover, the technological changes taking place in the internal and external environment has direct and indirect effects on the employee's performance (Haseeb, Hussain, Ślusarczyk, &Jermsittiparsert, 2019).

Managers, besides having extraordinary skills (technical, human and conceptual) and capabilities have to depend upon technology to fulfill their responsibilities (Gutierrez, Boukrami, &Lumsden, 2015) by using the artificial intelligence tools. These are the machines capable of performing tasks as human intelligence does, such as, visual perception, speech recognition, decision-making, and translation of languages. For this artificial intelligence and machine intelligence are the alternative terms used. It is the machine's intelligence , in contrast to the natural human intelligence. It is any device that perceives its environment and takes actions that maximize its chance of successfully achieving its goals (Russell, &Norvig, 2016).

On one side employee's work behaviors are becoming problematic, like work deviant behaviors (Craun, 2005) and to manage such behaviors the managers rely on the information got through machines (Shanks, Sinha, & Thomas, 2015). Machines provide accurate and authentic information (Thomas, Jones, & Faulkner, 2012). Therefore, the managers need to adapt technology for enhancing the skills set for better controls (Prieto & Perez-Santana, 2014) and to avoid the declining individual and organizational performance in the software development and other IT systems.

The social exchange theory views that employees work in efficient manner when an organization is taking care of them and supporting their performance at the workplace (Liao, et al., 2019; Ekeh, 1974), at the same time the organizational support theory support the functioning of employees and managers equally by using the artificial intelligence tools and techniques. Moreover, the organizations should support employees by providing

organizational recognition, generating internal motivation and good working results (Arthur, 1994) that is possible through having transparency in performance systems, i.e., the use of artificial intelligence systems.

No doubt, managers having adequate skills have a great influence on driving employee's performance (Shipper, & Davy, 2002) by guiding them and sharing the resources and by resolving the conflicts arising at workplace but due to heavy responsibilities they must rely on machines to tackle employee deviant behaviors (Marganski, & Fauth, 2013). The literature provides room for re-examining the Katz theory of managerial skills by reporting mixed results on technical, conceptual, and human skills having impact on performance. Few researchers argued that technical skills are detrimental to managing employees' others argued that the good manager-employee relationships are the basis for better individual and organizational performance. Further the prevalence of technology may also influence these relationships. This study aims to determine if technical skills provide any incremental value over interpersonal and conceptual skills in the performance of employees and explores potential moderation of the artificial intelligence in the relationship between managerial skills set suggested by Katz theory and performance of IT employees.

This study contributes two-fold in the literature. Firstly, by establishing the relationship of manager's skills and employee performance and secondly by testing the Katz theory of managerial skills in the context of artificial intelligence, the ever-emerging area in research and practice.

Literature review

Technical skills and Employee performance

Technical knowledge of the manager pertains to having knowledge about the functioning of the organization and the systems, machines and mechanisms used to run its operations effectively. Technical knowledge is strongly related to gauging employee's performance and to have better control. Having technical competencies help managers to overcome work related burden and completion of activities in time (Stevenson & Starkweather, 2010).

Additionally, in previous studies Prabhakar (2008) noted that organization and project success can be seen in terms of two aspects such as technical performance and manager's efficiency of executing those skills (Freeman & Beale, 1992). The technical skills possessed by the managers help them to guide the supervisees in times of mistakes and problems related to machines and systems installed (like the use of artificial intelligence), thus helping employees to do their work in a better way (Azadeh, Rouzbahmana, & Saberi, 2009).

The inconsistencies exist in the opinion of employees regarding the use of manager's technical skills, and they believe that the technical skills are least important in managing humans at the workplace as compared to their human and conceptual skills (Wu, & Wu, 2011) because the use of technology in the workplace causes stress and dissatisfaction among employees. The managers having excellent technical skills also excel in supervising individuals working under their supervision and such managers are generally rewarded for their "best and brightest" performance due to the use of their technical skills. Moreover the personality research argued that the personality characteristics that make good professionals with high technical skill are diametrically opposed to the characteristics that make good managers (Hysong, 2008), like interpersonal and communication skills.

Such managers become task oriented instead of people oriented giving less importance to the humans over machines thus losing the loyalty of employees but managing performance using technology overweigh other skills especially when it is about managing employee's performance in the IT firms. The technical skills may be a blessing or a boon for managing employees (Hysong, 2008). The un-conclusive arguments motivated researchers to develop hypothesis.

H1: The technical skills may have a positive relationship with employee performance of IT employees.

Human skills and employee performance

The interpersonal skills are universally accepted to have direct effect on the ability to interact and to get along with others through building important relationships and support functioning as a positive contributor to a teamwork. The interpersonal skills accumulate the communication effectiveness and way to approach and solve problems thus contributing to their success (Phiri, Bano, & Raouf, 2019). Such managers have the capability to know the way to communicate, motivate, lead, and inculcate enthusiasm and trust (Gana, & Ifah, 2012) among employees.

The human or interpersonal skills provide the opportunity to communicate with subordinates and colleagues to manage work related affairs at the workplace. Human skills are helpful in ensuring the use of strategies like compliance and commitment and informal networks are equally important than the formal networks in the organizations to have positive performance outcomes (Whelan, 2016). The managers with stronger interpersonal skills have low stress levels at their workplace and high commitment from their employees (Hysong, 2008). They can inspire their subordinates and can help them resolve conflicts at workplace and guide them to avoid adoption of work avoidant and deviant behaviors (Saraniya, & Thevaranjan, 2016). It is also observed that the

managers having too informal relationships may face problems of low productivity of employees due to having less control over them (Krackhardt, & Hanson, 1993).

At the same time the researchers have demonstrated that the successful influence outcomes are positively associated with rational persuasion and inspirational appeals but are negatively related to negative influencing tactics (Yukl, et al., 1996). The managers who use the interpersonal skills for guiding and motivating employees tend to have positive performance outcomes than the managers who try to negatively (use of position or power) influence people for their personal benefits or other outcomes (Bashir, 2017).

Quang, Khuong, and Le (2015) argued that a manager having capabilities to manage his own emotions are better manager over others. The human skills help in developing emotional employee-manager attachment and can resolve conflicts and ambiguities at the workplace. This also support adoption of changes occurring in environment and provide a competitive edge to the organization (Phiri, Bano, & Raouf, 2019). Based on the arguments the hypothesis developed is.

H2: The human skills may have a positive relationship with employee performance of IT employees.

Conceptual skills and Employee performance

The conceptual skills provide edge to have expert power in the field of work and the people get influenced by the information and ideas shared by their managers (Cooke, Cooper, Bartram, Wang, & Mei, 2019). Generally, the managers working at the top level use the conceptual skills but at the same time they use these skills to influence their subordinates (Gupta, 1996) by having capabilities to have timely decision and to manage portfolios for better individual and organizational outcomes. It helps the managers to establish a viable relationship between the cause and effect of any decision or action taken.

The conceptual skills provide strength for placing targets to be achieved and equipping employees with the deficient skills. The competent workforce is necessary for the organization and the managers having conceptual skills can enable employees to work effectively and in the right direction. The conceptual skills of a manager help building manager-employee work related trust relationships (David, & David, 2016).

The informational roles are performed using the conceptual skills and this can provide an edge to get the expert power for influencing and motivating employees to work better for the organization. This is directly related to employees having better performance. Butt, Waseem, Rafiq, Nawab, and Khilji (2014) argued that managers with cognitive skilled can establish good organizational values because of learning and mastering skills and have positive impact on productivity of employees. The conceptual skills are beneficial in building work-based trust besides developing relation based trust. Because the manager with conceptual skills can easily set the direction of organization and lack of conceptual skills can jeopardize the whole system as the achievement of the competitive edge based on time is directly related to the effective application of conceptual skills (Jacobs, & McGee, 2001; Cooke, Cooper, Bartram, Wang, & Mei, 2019). Based on the above arguments the hypothesis developed is;

H3: The conceptual skills may have a positive relationship with employee performance of IT employees.

Artificial intelligence (technology) as moderator

The use of artificial intelligence is becoming ever popular. It is the ability of a machine to sense, reason and respond to the environment. The computer algorithms are used to manage employee's performance (O'Connor, 2016) and the organizations are adopting this change to help managers manage their subordinates effectively (Gerslbeck, 2018).

The use of AI is encouraged in the organizations because of having access to huge amount of data, that humans, as managers, cannot handle solely and the ability of AI in supporting better decision making (Hughes, Robert, Frady, Arroyos, 2019) in most complex and dynamic competitive era. Employee's performance is key to the enhanced productivity of the organizations. AI helps in the adoption of the best managerial practices by utilizing the full potential of the organization (Shuck, Adelson, & Reio, 2017).

The theory X proposed that human beings are least interested to perform their work by showing least engagement in work (Carson, 2005). The managers at-times become helpless to manage huge number of less engaged employees and need some support from the artificial intelligence mechanisms for better performance outcomes. AI management systems seek to promote worker engagement by directing, monitoring, and rewarding or punishing employee's actions.

Employee behaviors and organizational controls have the ever-older relationship (Cardinal, et al., 2017). AI behavior controls encompass the monitoring and directing employees electronically to ensure their compliance with their job descriptions and roles defined. It is also possible that besides controlling the behaviors of the employees, managers may lose their trust in them, thus making the use of AI not exactly a blessing. It is necessary that the employees and employers must know what they want to achieve by using the systems like

artificial intelligence, thus saving their levels of trust (De Jong, & Elfring, 2010; Gefen, Karahanna, & Straub, 2003).

The arguments mentioned above helped in developing the following hypotheses.

H4: The Artificial intelligence systems/tools moderate the relationship between manager's technical skills and employee performance

H5: The Artificial intelligence systems/tools moderate the relationship between manager's human skills and employee performance

H6: The Artificial intelligence systems/tools moderate the relationship between manager's conceptual skills and employee performance

Framework

The composition of men, material and machines in an organization needs all aspects to be well articulated. The managerial skills are found to have adequate relationship with the use of organizational resources. At the same time besides having managerial capabilities the use of artificial intelligence techniques is becoming call for the current era. The Katz theory of managerial skills along with the emerging concept of artificial intelligence provided the foundations for developing the framework. The technology provides the power to have better control. The managers having too much informal relationships may face problems of low productivity of employees due to having less control over them (Krackhardt, & Hanson, 1993), here comes the role of artificial intelligence to remind managers and employees the goals set to be fulfilled. Although the Katz theory of managerial skills propose that the use of these skills is attached to the level of hierarchy of the organization, but it does not means at all that managers cannot use these skills simultaneously. The current framework is proposed based on testing the relationship of these skills with employee performance of the IT firms.

Figure 1: The framework developed for testing

Hypotheses:

H1: Manager's technical skills have positive relationship with employee performance.

H2: Manager's human skills have positive relationship with employee performance.

H3: Manager's conceptual skills have positive relationship with employee performance.

H4: Artificial intelligence systems/tools moderate the relationship between manager's technical skills and employee performance.

H5: Artificial intelligence tools moderate the relationship between manager's human skills and employee performance.

H6: Artificial intelligence tools moderate the relationship between manager's conceptual skills and employee performance.

Methodology

A convenience sample of 240 male and female middle level managers who worked for at-least two years in the same place and were still working full-time in that IT firm was used for this study. The quantitative approach with cross-sectional design was used to conduct this study. The questionnaires were adopted from (Prentice, Dominique Lopes, & Wang 2019) for measuring effects of artificial intelligence. The employee performance scale was used Koopmans, L., Brnaards, Hildebrandt, de Vet, and van der Beek, (2014) and managerial skills (technical, human, and conceptual) were assessed using Seyedinejat, Razaghi, and Dousti (2014) questionnaire. All the statements were assessed using five points Likert scale. The structural equation modeling was used with the help of SmartPLS software for assessing the relationships of the constructs. The IT firms were selected because gauging employee performance is a real concern for the top management and for this, they may use various tools such as artificial intelligence.

Results& Discussions

Table 1
Respondent's profile

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage	
Age (Years)	21-25	20		
	26-35	17		
	36-45	132		
	46-55	71		
	Total	240		
Attached to the same field 1-5 years		97	40.4	
	6-10 ears	173	57.1	
	>11 years	6	2.5	
	Total	240	100	
Gender	Female	100		
	Male	140		
	Total	240	100	
Education	Bachelors	38		
	Masters	44		
	MS	137		
	Ph. D.	21		
	Total	240	100	
Management level	Top	131		
	Middle			
	First-level			
	Total	240	100	

Table 1 explains that in total 240 respondents took part in the study and responded to the questionnaire distributed.

The Measurement Model

Table
Loadings, Cronbach's alpha, CR and AVE

Constructs	Loadings	Alpha	CR	AVE
Artificial Intelligence		0.856	0.884	0.558
AI1	0.727			
AI2	0.754			
AI3	0.737			
AI4	0.711			

AI5	0.734			
AI6	0.741			
AI7	0.766			
AI8	0.745			
AI9	0.758			
AI10	0.737			
AI11	0.712			
AI12	0.747			
AI13	0.742			
AI14	0.848			
AI15	0.722			
Technical skills		0.743	0.825	0.569
TS1	0.831			
TS2	0.738			
TS3	0.889			
TS4	0.850			
TS5	0.743			
TS6	0.813			
Human Skills		0.827	0.871	0.593
HS1	0.863			
HS2	0.706			
HS3	0.776			
HS4	0.785			
HS5	0.715			
HS6	0.765			
HS7	0.724			
Conceptual Skills		0.797	0.861	0.553
CS1	0.702			
CS2	0.818			
CS3	0.737			
CS4	0.717			
CS5	0.738			
Employee Performance		0.814	0.868	0.538
EP1	0.845			
EP2	0.854			
EP3	0.891			
EP4	0.840			
EP5	0.752			
EP6	0.708			

Source: Smartpls Output

Table
Fornell&Larcker criterion

	AI	CS	EP	HS	TS
AI	0.746				
CS	0.772	0.744			
EP	0.543	0.426	0.733		
HS	0.725	0.694	0.348	0.702	
TS	0.691	0.609	0.272	0.688	0.754

Source: Smartpls Results

The Structural model

The model fitness was examined using fitness indices like SRMR = 0.031, chi-Square = 763.767, and NFI = 0.923, showing the adequate model fitness. Moreover, the value of coefficient of determination shows that collectively the three skills brought about 45% change in the employee performance in the IT firms.

Table
Direct and Indirect Relationships

Relationship	Coefficient	t-value	p-value
AI -> EP	0.072	2.572	0.050
CS -> EP	0.251	2.257	0.024
HS -> EP	0.205	3.572	0.042
TS -> EP	0.242	3.509	0.051
Moderating Effect			
1 -> EP	0.183	3.009	0.031
Moderating Effect			
2 -> EP	0.164	0.642	0.521
Moderating Effect			
3 -> EP	0.136	2.819	0.032

Source: SmartPLS Results, 1 = TS, 2 = HS, 3 = CS.

The results show that the direct relationships are positive and significant. The technical skills of managers (beta = 0.242, $p > 0.05$) have a positive and significant relationship with employee performance. Similarly, the human skills (beta = 0.205, $p > 0.05$) and conceptual skills (beta = 0.251, $p > 0.05$). Additionally, the relationship of using artificial intelligence tools and employee performance is examined that also resulted in positive relationships (beta = 0.072, $p = 0.050$) showing positive and significant relationship.

Further the moderating effects are examined that show that the artificial intelligence moderates the relationship between technical skills (beta = 0.183, $p = 0.051$) and employee performance as well as the conceptual skills (beta = 0.136, $p > 0.050$) and employee performance but the artificial failed to moderate between human skills (beta = 0.164, $p < 0.050$) and employee performance.

Discussion and conclusion

The study aimed at examining the relationship of managerial technical, human and conceptual skills on employee performance in IT sector of Pakistan with moderating effects of use of artificial tools. The results revealed that three of the managerial skills help employees enhance their performance. The moderation results show that the artificial intelligence tools moderate the relationship of technical and conceptual skills with employee performance but failed to moderate between human skills and performance (Shipper, & Davy, 2002). The results for the direct relationships examined are consistent with earlier findings (Phiri, Bano, & Raouf, 2019; Haseeb, Hussain, Ślusarczyk, & Jermsittiparsert, 2019; Buil, Martínez, & Matute, 2019). Further the results of the current study confirmed the Katz theory of managerial skills. All the technical, human and conceptual skills are important to manage the employee's performance of IT firms. On one side the human skills, possessed by the managers, provide them the opportunity to deal effectively with the employees and fulfillment of other relational needs, highlighted by the Maslow's hierarchy of needs theory (Shanks, Sinha, & Thomas, 2015). People who satisfy their relational needs are found to have better satisfaction and are good performers. They tend to have better relations with others and can persuade the subordinates easily (Shanks, Sinha, & Thomas, 2015).

The artificial intelligence tools one side help managers to gauge employee performance and on the other hand it help in managing customers' demands and choices (Russell, & Norvig, 2016). It is likely that employees who feel threat in the presence of AI systems they may develop a sense of mistrust and may try to hide their actual potential, besides their managers having a best collection of skills (Rizwan, Tariq, Hassan, & Sultan, 2014). It is noted from the results of the current study, artificial intelligence systems do not help in using the human skills effectively by managers. It means that the use of systems and technology may reduce the levels of trust that are needed to perform better by the employees (Reb, Chaturvedi, Narayanan, & Kudesia, 2019).

Finally, it is concluded that all the managerial skills suggested by the Katz theory are beneficial for the employee performance and the presence of artificial intelligence support the relationship managerial skills and performance.

Implications

The combination of skills possessed by managers make them perfect, but the addition of artificial intelligence tools adds to their synergy. The artificial intelligence may also be used as an influencing tool to shape employee performance. At the same time employees who want to have transparency in their work systems and want fair distribution of awards and rewards may also prefer the prevalence of artificial intelligence tools. The employees should not only perform their duties due to threat of the AI systems but try their best to perform their duties with interest and commitment for individual and organizational effectiveness.

The more employees have trust in their managers and the use of AI systems by their managers they will be able to take more advice and guidance form these systems and try to remove errors from their work thus enhancing their performance. The use of AI systems should be made with caution. It must not hamper the trust levels of the managers and employees. The managers having best set of skills at-times fail to reap the best results by using AI systems that should not be the case in the IT firms, where there is need to work in collaboration with managers.

Limitations and Future directions

The data was gathered from a single sector where the use of managerial skills and artificial intelligence tools has great importance that is the IT organizations. Few constructs were considered for testing a developed model with a single medium of collecting data. The multiple sources of gathering responses will reduce the single method bias for the future studies. The framework test may also include the other aspects of employees like their engagement and commitment while examining their performance in the presence of artificial intelligence systems. Further the study on multiple sectors may also reap fruitful results.

References

- Azadeh, A., Rouzbahmana, M., &Saber, M. (2009). Utilization of an Artificial Intelligence approach for Assessment of Job satisfaction. *International Journal of Intelligent Information Technology Application*, 2(6), 1-10.
- Bashir, F. M. (2017). An analysis of managerial competencies and their influence on staff productivity: A case of Wajir County Government employees. *Human Resource and Leadership Journal*, 2(2), 81-107.
- Buil, I., Martínez, E., &Matute, J. (2019). Transformational leadership and employee performance: The role of identification, engagement and proactive personality. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 77, 64-75.
- Cardinal, L. B., Kreutzer, M., & Miller, C. C. (2017). An aspirational view of organizational control research: Re-invigorating empirical work to better meet the challenges of 21st century organizations. *Academy of Management Annals*, 11, 559- 592
- Carson, C. M. (2005). A historical view of Douglas McGregor's theory Y. *Management Decision*, 43, 450-460.
- Cooke, F. L., Cooper, B., Bartram, T., Wang, J., & Mei, H. (2019). Mapping the relationships between high-performance work systems, employee resilience and engagement: A study of the banking industry in China. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 30(8), 1239-1260.
- Craun, E. D. (2005). *Lies, Slander and Obscenity in Medieval English Literature: Pastoral Rhetoric and the Deviant Speaker*(Vol. 31). Cambridge University Press.
- David, F., & David, F. R. (2016). *Strategic management: A competitive advantage approach, concepts and cases*. Pearson–Prentice Hall.
- De Jong, B. A., &Elfring, T. (2010). How trust affects performance of ongoing teams. *Academy of Management Journal*, 53, 535-549.
- Gana, A. B., &Ifah, S. S. (2012). The effects of managerial skills on staff efficiency and effectiveness in organizations. *Journal of Management and Corporate Governance*, 4, 58-70.'
- Gefen, D., Karahanna, E., & Straub, D. W. (2003). Trust and TAM in online shopping: an integrated model. *MIS Quarterly*, 27(1), 51-90.
- Gerlsbeck, R. (2018). The AI manager. *Smith Magazine*, Summer Issue. Retrieved from <https://smith.queensu.ca/magazine/summer-2018/features/ai-manager>.
- Gupta, S. (1996). Managerial effectiveness: Conceptual framework and scale development. *Indian journal of industrial Relations*, 31(3), 392-409.
- Gutierrez, A., Boukrami, E., & Lumsden, R. (2015). Technological, organisational and environmental factors influencing managers' decision to adopt cloud computing in the UK. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, 1(10), 1-10.
- Haseeb, M., Hussain, H. I., Ślusarczyk, B., &Jermisittiparsert, K. (2019). Industry 4.0: A solution towards technology challenges of sustainable business performance. *Social Sciences*, 8(5), 154.
- Hughes, C., Robert, L., Frady, K., Arroyos, A., (2019), "Artificial Intelligence, Employee Engagement, Fairness, and Job Outcomes", *Managing Technology and Middle- and Low-skilled Employees (The Changing Context of Managing People)*, Emerald Publishing Limited, pp. 61-68

- Hysong, S. J. (2008). The role of technical skill in perceptions of managerial performance. *Journal of Management Development*, 27(3), 275-290.
- Jacobs, T. O., & McGee, M. L. (2001). Competitive advantage: Conceptual imperatives for executives.
- Marganski, A., & Fauth, K. (2013). Socially interactive technology and contemporary dating: A cross cultural exploration of deviant behaviors among young adults in the modern, evolving technological world. *International Criminal Justice Review*, 23(4), 357-377.
- O' Connor, S. (2016, September). When your boss is an algorithm. Financial Times. Retrieved from <https://www.ft.com/content/88fdc58e-754f-11e6-b60a-de4532d5ea35>
- Phiri, A., Bano, N., & Raouf, A. (2019). Interpersonal skills and emotion management: Impact of social leadership on job satisfaction of workers. *Advances in Developmental and Educational Psychology*, 1(1), 1-6.
- Prentice, C., Dominique Lopes, S., & Wang, X. (2019). Emotional intelligence or artificial intelligence—an employee perspective. *Journal of Hospitality Marketing & Management*, 1-27.
- Reb, J., Chaturvedi, S., Narayanan, J., & Kudesia, R. S. (2019). Leader mindfulness and employee performance: a sequential mediation model of LMX quality, interpersonal justice, and employee stress. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 160(3), 745-763.
- Rizwan, M., Tariq, M., Hassan, R., & Sultan, A. (2014). A comparative analysis of the factors effecting the employee motivation and employee performance in Pakistan. *International Journal of Human Resource Studies*, 4(3), 35-38.
- Russell, S. J., & Norvig, P. (2016). *Artificial intelligence: a modern approach*. Malaysia; Pearson Education Limited.
- Shanks, R., Sinha, S., & Thomas, R. J. (2015). Managers and machines, unite. *Accenture Institute for High Performance and Accenture Strategy*.
- Shipper, F., & Davy, J. (2002). A model and investigation of managerial skills, employees' attitudes, and managerial performance. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 13(2), 95-120.
- Shuck, B., Adelson, J. L., & Reio, T. G. (2017). The employee engagement scale: Initial evidence for construct validity and implications for theory and practice. *Human Resource Management*, 56, 953-977.
- Thomas, S., Jones, D. G., & Faulkner, A. (2012). *U.S. Patent No. 8,176,178*. Washington, DC: U.S. Patent and Trademark Office.
- Wu, L. C., & Wu, M. (2011). Employee dissatisfaction with organizational change: An Empirical study of a technology services company. *African Journal of Business Management*, 5(4), 1304.

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